

SUSTAINABLE PHASE CHANGING FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable composites made of a thermoplastic polyphenylene sulfide matrix reinforced with recycled carbon fibers were produced and infiltrated with a bio-based phase change material to enhance their temperature resistance. By varying molding pressure, the void content of the composites was controlled, thereby allowing for variable phase change material content. Flexural testing revealed that the inclusion of phase change material enhances the flexural modulus of the composites. Similarly, the thermal conductivity of the composites was found to improve with the addition of phase change material, which filled the pore spaces within the composite that prevented effective heat transfer. While typically viewed as a detriment, we showed that targeted porosity infiltrated with a phase change material can enhance the functionality of composites with minimum flexural stiffness loss.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymers are the material of choice for high performance structures subjected to moderate thermal loads. For more intense thermal loading, microvascular composites offer sustained high temperature performance that is otherwise limited by the polymeric matrix[1]. However, structures do not always undergo sustained thermomechanical loading, instead often experiencing brief temperature excursions during operation in applications such as batteries and motors in electric vehicles and aircraft during acceleration or take-off/landing. As such, the active cooling of composites may not always be the most appropriate design choice due to the additional complexity and weight associated with the hardware required to actively pump the coolant through vasculature. Phase change materials (PCMs) offer a passive alternative to active cooling.

Few authors have studied the use of PCMs as a means of thermal regulation in composite materials. Casado et al.[2] filled cavities in an injection molded rail flanged plate with PCM to extend fatigue life by more than 400% through reduced temperature rise of the polyamide matrix. Yoo et al. [3,4] incorporated PCM microcapsules into a glass fiber/epoxy laminate to enhance thermal energy storage. They found that the PCM led to a decrease in thermal conductivity, an increase in thermal storage capacity, an increase in dimensional stability, and a significant decrease in the mechanical properties of the composites. The thermal stability of the composites was unaffected by the inclusion of PCM. Fredi et al. [5] mixed paraffin microcapsules into carbon fiber/PMMA composites and found that the activation energy of PCM composite glass transition was not significantly impacted by the PCM with a melting point of 43 °C. Their dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) results indicated that the embedded PCM caused a brief pause in the gradual storage modulus decrease during heating.

In this study, we investigated the manufacturing of recycled carbon fiber composites containing embedded phase change materials. Unlike the prior work, which focused primarily on microcapsules mixed into the resin, we show that low-cost sustainable composites containing PCM can be produced using a scalable vacuum infiltration process. We showed that recycled carbon fiber nonwoven preforms can be used to manufacture composites with highly connected porosity when processed by compression molding following the author's prior work[6]. Recycled carbon fibers offer a significant reduction in carbon emissions, while maintaining near virgin fiber mechanical properties. The PPS matrix offers high toughness, solvent resistance, and is commonly found in under-the-hood automotive applications. We

produced samples with varying molding pressures and resin content to induce varying void content, which was characterized by density measurements and optical microscopy. We filled the connected pore space with a bio-based PCM having a heat storage capacity near 200 J g^{-1} using a vacuum infiltration process. We then characterized flexural performance and transverse thermal conductivity. This work sets the foundation for creating multifunctional composites for thermal energy storage using sustainable reinforcement and PCMs.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Carbon Fiber

Recycled carbon fiber preforms, provided by Gen2 Carbon (formerly ELG Carbon Fibre), containing fibers recovered via a pyrolysis process and then upcycled into a nominally 200 gm^{-2} nonwoven fabric produced using carding and cross-lapping processes, were used in this work. Prior testing revealed that the fibers exhibit standard modulus properties[7]. Fiber length was greater than 25 mm, for which mechanical properties significantly exceeding typical short fiber composites have been realized. The use of recycled carbon fibers makes this reinforcement choice both low cost and sustainable. Reducing manufacturing waste and re-using fibers from end-of-life parts aids in the development of a circular economy for composite materials.

2.2 Polyphenylene Sulfide

Polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) is a semicrystalline aromatic thermoplastic offering high toughness, solvent resistance, and performance comparable to many common structural epoxies. The high melt temperature of the polymer, in combination with the high levels of crystallinity that enables its use well beyond its glass transition temperature, makes PPS a strong candidate for applications in which thermal resilience is required. PPS films of 0.127 mm thickness (Solvay, Ryton QC160P) were purchased from CS Hyde for use as the matrix in the composites manufactured in this study. In addition to the beneficial thermal, mechanical, and chemical properties of PPS, the recyclability of thermoplastic matrix composites is of key importance to the development of a circular economy for composite materials. PPS can be melt processed to form new composites from end-of-life components and manufacturing waste[8], unlike traditional thermosets that are typically pyrolyzed or chemically digested for fiber recovery and subsequent integration into new parts.

2.3 Phase Change Materials

A commercially-available PCM was purchased (Entropy Solutions, PureTemp). The material, referred to as 48X, was a white wax as a solid and a clear, low viscosity liquid as a melt. According to the manufacturer, the 48X PCM shows a melting point of $48 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a thermal conductivity of $0.25 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and a heat storage capacity of 230 J g^{-1} . PCMs are emerging as an option to improve the thermal efficiency of buildings through thermal energy storage[9]. Their integration into low-cost composite materials would enable new architectural designs with enhanced sustainability.

2.4 Composite Manufacturing

Composites were manufactured through a compression molding process. Relative to traditional composite manufacturing techniques such as autoclave and oven curing of thermosets, compression molding is a rapid and low energy process capable of meeting high volume demand. First, organosheets, or single plies of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic, were produced by compressing a single nonwoven layer between two PPS films at $300 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 1 MPa pressure for 5 minutes, followed by cooling under pressure to $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The organosheets were then cut into $150 \text{ mm} \times 150 \text{ mm}$ plies and placed in a closed mold of the same dimensions to form plaques for testing. Due to anisotropy in the preforms[6], special care was taken to track the laminate orientation. Processing times and temperatures were the same for organosheets and composite plaques, while the pressure used to manufacture plaques was varied from 0.5 to 4 MPa to achieve differing levels of porosity.

Samples were cut from the plaques for flexural, thermal conductivity, and dynamic mechanical analysis testing using a wet diamond saw and subsequently milled to the final dimensions. Once at the

final dimensions, the density of the composites was evaluated using an analytical balance and measurements of the length, width, and thickness. Some of the samples were evaluated as-cut, while others were infiltrated with the PCM before testing. Initial density measurements using a helium pycnometer revealed that the porosity within the uninfiltrated samples was highly connected. PCM infiltration was achieved by placing the samples in a beaker of PCM melt inside a vacuum oven for 10 minutes at greater than 26" Hg.

2.5 Micrographic Analysis

Specimens extracted from the plaques were polished for optical microscopy. Images were acquired at 200X resolution (0.96 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) over a 12.7 mm wide section of the composites using a Keyence VHX-7100 automated stage microscope. The fiber volume fraction was determined by segmenting the images in ImageJ and using a pixel-counting script developed in MATLAB. This method has been shown to yield good agreement with measurements using Archimede's Principle[7]. Multiple cross sections were evaluated to capture local variability.

2.6 Flexural Testing

Flexural testing was performed on samples according to the ASTM D790 standard on specimens of 50.8 mm \times 12.7 mm at a span-to-depth ratio of 16 at a strain rate of 1% per minute. Five samples containing PCM and five neat samples were tested per molding condition. Additionally, neat PCM samples were tested.

2.7 Thermal Conductivity

Transverse (through-thickness) thermal conductivity was measured using the double-sided transient plane source method (TPS 2500S, Hot Disk). Three measurements were taken per sample at each molding pressure on neat samples. The neat samples were then infiltrated with PCM and re-tested to ensure that local microstructural variability did not significantly influence the measurement.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Multiscale Characteristics

The composites were evaluated at both the bulk and microstructure scales to elucidate the effects of varying pressure during molding. The density of the composites was found to increase as a function of the applied molding pressure, as shown in Figure 1. Previous work by the author[10] has shown that increasing the molding pressure leads to greater fiber compaction and enhanced consolidation. Too little pressure leads to porosity due to resin starvation. Interestingly, the density measured by helium pycnometry was largely consistent, ranging from 1.482 to 1.507 g/cc. The void-free density was estimated to be 1.494 g/cc based on the densities of the constituent components. This indicates that the pores within the composite were highly connected.

The void content before and after infiltration with the PCM is also shown in Figure 1. A major reduction in void content was apparent when comparing the measured density for PCM infiltrated composites with the theoretical density of a composite in which all the voids were filled with PCM. For samples molded at pressures of 2 and 4 MPa, the initial porosity was so low that the PCM had no significant effect on further decreasing porosity. This indicates that there is a limit to the pore connectivity in the composites.

Figure 1: Additional molding pressure significantly increases composite density (left) and most of the voids are filled with PCM (right).

Example optical micrographs acquired for the samples are shown in Figure 2 and the resulting fiber volume fraction analysis is found in Table 1. For low molding pressure, significant interlaminar voids are present, indicating that resin migrated either from the center of the preforms and toward the interfaces or from the interfaces and to the center during consolidation. The high loft of recycled carbon fiber nonwovens makes this behavior likely to occur, although additional study is required to understand the mechanism. As the pressure increased to 1 MPa, the voids became more dispersed and spherical in shape, indicating entrapped gas as opposed to resin migration. At and above 2 MPa, the voids were nearly gone, with a consistent distribution of fibers. Likewise, the fiber volume fraction was a function of the total applied pressure, in addition to the matrix film thickness. The maximum was achieved at or beyond 2 MPa molding pressure, representing complete infiltration of the matrix film. The fiber content saturates at this level as there is no way of removing excess resin in the closed mold used in this study. For discontinuous fiber composites, this represents a significant improvement over incumbent materials such as long fiber thermoplastics and injection molding compounds.

Figure 2: Representative micrographs of compression molded composites before infiltration.

Molding Pressure	Fiber Volume Fraction (%)
0.5 MPa	27.73 ± 1.64
1 MPa	26.89 ± 1.77
2 MPa	35.25 ± 2.23
4 MPa	33.65 ± 1.51

Table 1: Fiber volume fraction measured from optical micrographs

3.2 Flexural Testing

Flexural testing of the neat PCM revealed extremely low mechanical properties. The flexural strength was 1.17 MPa ± 0.019 MPa and the flexural modulus was 0.41 GPa ± 0.09 GPa. A simple Rule of Mixtures approximation for the properties of the infiltrated composites is as follows:

$$P_{infiltrated} = P_{composite}(1 - V_{PCM}) + P_{PCM}V_{PCM} \quad (1)$$

where P refers to the property (strength or modulus) of interest for the composite or PCM phase and V refers to the volume fraction of each phase. Due to the small volume of PCM and its low mechanical properties compared to the composite, the PCM is not expected to contribute significantly to the mechanical properties of the infiltrated composites.

Surprisingly, flexural testing of the composites revealed a significant increase in modulus in the samples containing PCM, as shown in Figure 3. This modulus increase cannot be simply explained by the Rule of Mixtures but instead is likely the result of more complex micromechanical mechanisms that require further exploration. It is theorized that the filled voids may provide an elastic support for fibers subjected to bending within the composite. Due to the small fiber diameter, bending of fibers near voids is expected to be significant. By filling the void with PCM, the neighboring fibers can be supported against bending. Future work will be required to evaluate this proposed mechanism of stiffness retention.

The flexural strength of the composites was not significantly improved by the addition of PCM, indicating that the reduction in void space did little to change the failure of the composites. This behavior is expected from the Rule of Mixtures, as the strength of the neat PCM was very low relative to the composite strength. It is worth noting the error bars in Figure 3. The variability in properties is more significant for the composites manufactured at lower molding pressures. Much of this variability may be attributed to the microstructural inhomogeneity in discontinuous fiber composites, in which regions of fiber misorientation or variable fiber volume fraction may lead to premature localized failure that is amplified by inhomogeneous void distribution. Hence, the lower the void content, the less variable the strength. The variability in this work could be better understood with further testing that is beyond the scope of this manuscript. Despite this limitation, the trends are clear: the flexural strength of composites infiltrated with PCM is largely unaffected, while their flexural modulus generally improves.

Figure 3: Flexural strength (top) and modulus (bottom) of neat and PCM-containing composites manufactured at different molding pressures.

3.3 Thermal Conductivity

The measured transverse thermal conductivity of the composites is shown in Figure 4. The thermal conductivity of the neat PPS was reported as $0.30 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ by the manufacturer. The transverse thermal conductivity of composites is matrix-dominated due to the matrix regions separating fibers. Furthermore, the transverse thermal conductivity of carbon fibers is typically much lower than the axial thermal conductivity. Due to these properties, in combination with the high void content of the composites manufactured at low molding pressures, the thermal conductivity of composites molded below 2 MPa was lower than even the neat polymer. However, the addition of PCM to fill the porosity led to a significant increase in the transverse thermal conductivity of the composites despite its low thermal conductivity. For all molding pressures tested, the infiltrated composites reached approximately their full thermal conductivity with the addition of PCM.

Figure 4: Thermal conductivity of neat and PCM-containing composites manufactured at different molding pressures.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we developed low-cost, sustainable composites containing embedded phase change materials. The use of low-cost recycled carbon fiber reinforcement, an easily recyclable thermoplastic matrix, and rapid compression molding processing makes such materials attractive to high volume markets in which cycle and time and cost are key factors driving decision making. We showed that porosity in these composites can be controlled by varying the applied pressure during molding. After molding, parts can be vacuum infiltrated with a PCM melt in a scalable process. The embedded PCM offers several benefits, including synergistically enhanced flexural modulus and improved thermal conductivity. The PCM is also anticipated to enable brief excursions beyond typical use temperatures or sensing through thermal energy storage. This work shifts the paradigm of void content in composites from a detriment to a beneficial feature. Beyond the ability to withstand brief thermal excursions, this material system also adds passive thermal energy storage capabilities. The addition of PCM into sustainable composites may aid in an acceleration of the shift to composite materials in the transportation and construction industries by integrating additional thermal regulation capabilities without the need for active coolant pumping.

Future work will seek to evaluate the pore morphology of these composites, understand the impact of the embedded PCM on the activation energy of transition processes in the composites, and exploring the viscoelastic and fatigue properties of these materials. The use of recycled carbon fibers paired with a thermoplastic matrix and bio-based PCM makes this material a strong candidate for low carbon footprint multifunctional composites.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Coppola AM, Warpinski LG, Murray SP, Sottos NR, White SR. Survival of actively cooled microvascular polymer matrix composites under sustained thermomechanical loading. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **82**, 2016, pp. 170–9. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.12.010>).
- [2] Casado JA, Gutiérrez-Solana F, Carrascal I, Diego S, Polanco JA, Hernández D. Fatigue behavior enhancement of short fiber glass reinforced polyamide by adding phase change

- materials. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **93**, 2016, pp. 115–22. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2016.02.059>).
- [3] Yoo S, Kandare E, Shanks R, Al-Maadeed MA, Afaghi Khatibi A. Thermophysical properties of multifunctional glass fibre reinforced polymer composites incorporating phase change materials. *Thermochimica Acta*, **642**, 2016, pp. 25–31. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tca.2016.09.003>).
- [4] Yoo S, Kandare E, Mahendrarajah G, Al-Maadeed MA, Khatibi AA. Mechanical and thermal characterisation of multifunctional composites incorporating phase change materials. *Journal of Composite Materials*, **51**, 2017, pp. 2631–42. (<https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998316673894>).
- [5] Fredi G, Dorigato A, Pegoretti A. Dynamic-mechanical response of carbon fiber laminates with a reactive thermoplastic resin containing phase change microcapsules. *Mechanics of Time-Dependent Materials*, **24**, 2020, pp. 395–418. (<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11043-019-09427-y>).
- [6] Barnett PR, Gilbert CL, Penumadu D. Repurposed/recycled discontinuous carbon fiber organosheet development and composite properties. *Composites Part C: Open Access*, **4**, 2021. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcomc.2020.100092>).
- [7] Barnett PR, Young SA, Chawla V, Foster DM, Penumadu D. Thermo-mechanical Characterization of Discontinuous Recycled/Repurposed Carbon Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Organosheet Composites. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2021. (<https://doi.org/10.1177/00219983211015721>).
- [8] Barnett PR, Hmeidat NS, Zheng B, Penumadu D. Toward a circular economy: zero-waste manufacturing of carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites. *Npj Materials Sustainability*, **2**, 2024, pp. 1–12. (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s44296-024-00006-y>).
- [9] Faraj K, Khaled M, Faraj J, Hachem F, Castelain C. Phase change material thermal energy storage systems for cooling applications in buildings: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, **119**, 2020, pp. 109579. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109579>).
- [10] Barnett PR, Cook ZA, Hulett BM, Varma NH, Penumadu D. Influence of processing parameters on permeability and infiltration of compression molded discontinuous carbon fiber organosheet composites. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **152**, 2022, pp. 106682. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2021.106682>).